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Transfer of a mutant plant glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase gene from the nuclear to the plastid genome confers gabaculine resistance in tobacco --Manuscript Draft--

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Corresponding Author:	Daniele Rosellini, Ph.D University of Perugia Perugia, ITALY	
Corresponding Author Secondary Information:		
Corresponding Author's Institution:	University of Perugia	
Corresponding Author's Secondary Institution:		
First Author:	Michele Bellucci	
First Author Secondary Information:		
Order of Authors:	Michele Bellucci	
	Francesca De Marchis	
	Andrea Pompa	
	Maurizio Micheli	
	Tiziano Gardi	
	Daniele Rosellini, Ph.D	
Order of Authors Secondary Information:		
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Abstract:	<p>Plastid genome transformation is a powerful technology for engineering plant metabolism and producing useful compounds. New selection systems are required to extend plastid transformation to a more significant number of plant species. After demonstrating that a bacterial mutant glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase (GSA) gene is functional in tobacco plastids and confers resistance to the phytotoxin gabaculine, in this work, we transformed the tobacco plastome with a mutated GSA gene derived from alfalfa, along with the aadA selectable marker gene conferring spectinomycin resistance. Selection exploiting gabaculine was not effective to directly regenerate transplastomic events, but some events regenerated using conventional spectinomycin selection acquired gabaculine resistance during the second or third regeneration rounds with gabaculine selection, and the homoplasmic condition was attained. Gabaculine selection with our plant mutant GSA gene can be further investigated for plastid transformation of species that are not transformable with the aadA-spectinomycin selection system, and are more sensitive to gabaculine than tobacco.</p>	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Below we copied the questions and comments from Associate Editor and two reviewers, and provided responses to all of them.</p> <p>ASSOCIATE EDITOR</p> <p>Though the comments/suggestions of both reviewers are positive, I found this</p>	

manuscript is very similar with the paper "Bellucci, M., De Marchis, F., Ferradini, N., Pompa, A., Veronesi, F., & Rosellini, D. (2015). A mutant *Synechococcus* gene encoding glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase confers gabaculine resistance when expressed in tobacco plastids. *Plant cell reports*, 34(12), 2127-2136." The *Plant cell reports* paper tested glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase from *Synechococcus*. The current manuscript tested glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase from alfalfa. The results and conclusions of the two works are a bit too close. The authors must provide a clear explanation about the novelty in this report compared to their previous one or either state that this is the extension of previous studies to another species. I suggest the authors to transform this from an Original Paper into a Research Note.

RESPONSES

In fact, this is an extension of our previous study, aimed at replacing a bacterial gene with an orthologous plant gene as a selectable marker for tobacco plastid transformation.

We clearly stated this at page 2: "In this work, we inserted a mutated plant GSA gene into the tobacco plastome to indirectly compare its performance with the bacterial hemL gene, thus extending and confirming previous results."

We shortened the paper and moved two figures to the Supplementary materials to meet the space limitation of a Research Note.

REVIEWER #1

1 The concentration of gabaculine used in the selective medium is 50 μ M. Why use 50 μ M? In figure 2, could the transformed explants growth due to the gabaculine concentration?

2 In figure 5, when plants were selected on gabaculine, the growth of 5.2g was worse than 5.2s, Why?

RESPONSES

Question 1. Gabaculine concentration was chosen based on the cited Gough et al 2001 paper, and on our previous experience (Ferradini et al 2011; Bellucci et al. 2015). If we interpret well the referee's question, gabaculine resistance conferred by the mutant MsGSAgr gene is not complete in alfalfa, and resistant embryos are pale green (Ferradini et al 2011). The same occurs in tobacco plastid transformation (this work); therefore resistant shoots in Fig. 2 are smaller and paler than with spectinomycin selection, while the non-transformed shoots are yellow.

Question 2. After the second regeneration, the difference between 5.2s and 5.2g when grown on gabaculine is due to chimerism of 5.2g, as shown in the Southern blot of new Figure 2a-b. However, if the reviewer refers to the seeds of the plants deriving from the third regeneration cycle, the differences between 5.2g and 5.2s are only due to the seeding density on the plate, that was lower for 5.s. In fact, the size and color of the seedlings is the same: they are all green and healthy.

REVIEWER #2

The manuscript describes the use of the alfalfa mutant GSA and gabaculine for the generation of transplastomic plants in tobacco. The authors have shown that MsGSAgr behaves as a secondary selectable marker gene. Although gabaculine selection did not lead to direct regeneration of transplastomic events, some plants regenerated using spectinomycin selection acquired gabaculine resistance after the second or third rounds of selection with gabaculine.

The work is interesting in that the gene is from an important forage species, alfalfa. The results are well presented and the manuscript is well written. I suggest the following minor modifications:

1. page 3, line 94, change "Based on this result" to "Based on the above results".

RESPONSE: entire phrase was modified when transforming the submission from Original Article to Research Note

2. Page 5, line 183, "and reared in pots to flowering" may be changed to " and seeds were produced"

RESPONSE: the sentence has been changed in "seeds were produced"

3. In the discussion section, it will be helpful to have a brief discussion excluding the possibility of nuclear integration, although such a discussion is not essential.

RESPONSE: the discussion section has been largely deleted and reduced when transforming the submission from Original Article to Research Note, therefore there is no space to discuss this point. However, at page 7 we added the sentence "As expected, lack of resistance was shown in the reciprocal cross, excluding the possibility of expression from transgene nuclear integration."

In fact, if the transgenes were integrated in the nucleus, and expressed, the progenies of the cross NT x 5.2g should segregate for resistance to the two toxins and some seedlings (at least 25%) should be green.

Moreover, at page 6, we clarify that the possibility of nuclear integration present in the manuscript is referred to ancient wild plastid DNA "An additional faint 4.5 kb fragment was visible in all the homoplasmic plants, whereas in the heteroplasmic or wild-type plants either it was absent or hidden by the more abundant 4.4 kb fragment (Fig. 2b). As already observed (Bellucci et al. 2015), this fragment could indicate a WILD plastid DNA insertion in the nuclear genome or recombination between the endogenous and the inserted Prn promoters". In any case, such a nuclear insertion would not lead to resistance to gabaculine or spectinomycin.

[Click here to view linked References](#)

1 **TITLE PAGE**

2

3 **Transfer of a mutant plant glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase gene from the nuclear**
4 **to the plastid genome confers gabaculine resistance in tobacco**

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6 Michele Bellucci¹ ORCID 0000-0001-7476-9603

7 Francesca De Marchis¹ ORCID 0000-0002-1561-369X

8 Andrea Pompa^{1,3} ORCID

9 Maurizio Micheli² ORCID 0000-0002-5988-1952

10 Tiziano Gardi² ORCID 0000-0001-8194-5628

11 Daniele Rosellini² ORCID 0000-0002-8473-7012

12

13 ¹ Institute of Biosciences and Bioresources, Research Division of Perugia, National Research
14 Council (CNR), via della Madonna Alta 130, 06128 Perugia, Italy

15

16 ² Department of Agricultural Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, Borgo XX
17 Giugno 74, 06121 Perugia, Italy

18

19 ³Present Address: Department of Biomolecular Sciences, Section Plant Biology, University of
20 Urbino "Carlo Bo", via Bramante 48, 61029 Urbino, Italy.

21

22 **Corresponding Author**

23 Daniele Rosellini

24 daniele.rosellini@unipg.it

25 Tel. +39 0t55856211

26

27 **Key message**

28 Resistance to the phytotoxin gabaculine was obtained in tobacco by introducing a mutant plant gene
29 in the plastid genome; it may be implemented as a tool in plastid genetic transformation.

30

31 **Acknowledgment**

32 This work was funded by the Department of Agricultural Food and Environmental Sciences of the
33 University of Perugia, project: "Ricerca di base 2015: Sviluppo di un nuovo gene marcatore
34 selezionabile di origine vegetale per la trasformazione del genoma plastidiale". This work has been
35 conducted under the auspices of Consorzio Interuniversitario per le Biotecnologie (CIB).

36

37 **Conflict of Interest**

38 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

39

40 **Authors contribution**

41 DR and MB designed the study, MB, FDM, AP, MM, TG carried out the experiments; DR and MB
42 wrote the manuscript; all Authors revised the manuscript.

Abstract

~~Plastid genome transformation is a powerful technology for engineering plant metabolism and producing useful compounds.~~ New selection systems are required to extend plastid transformation to a more significant number of plant species. After demonstrating that a bacterial mutant glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase (GSA) gene is functional in tobacco plastids and confers resistance to the phytotoxin gabaculine, in this work, we transformed the tobacco plastome with a mutated GSA gene derived from alfalfa, along with the *aadA* selectable marker gene conferring spectinomycin resistance. Selection exploiting gabaculine was not effective to directly regenerate transplastomic events, but some events regenerated using conventional spectinomycin selection acquired gabaculine resistance during the second or third regeneration rounds with gabaculine selection, ~~and the homoplasmic condition was attained.~~ Gabaculine selection with our plant mutant GSA gene can be further investigated for plastid transformation of species that are not transformable with the *aadA*-spectinomycin selection system, ~~and are more sensitive to gabaculine than tobacco.~~

Key words Chloroplast; *In vitro* selection; gabaculine; Transgenic plants; Transplastomic plants

Introduction

~~Selectable marker genes (SMGs) are an essential tool for plant genetic engineering, allowing to select transgenic cells amid a large majority of non transgenic cells.~~ For the transformation of the plastid genome transformation, fourteen selectable marker genes (SMGs) have been reported (Rosellini 2012; Bock 2015; Tabatabaei et al. 2017) but only a handful are applicable to transformation of higher plants, and only the *E. coli aadA* gene (Goldschmidt-Clermont 1991), conferring spectinomycin resistance, has shown enough efficiency and versatility. This restricted choice of efficient selection systems and SMGs is considered one of the reasons why plastid transformation cannot still be accomplished in many crop species, especially cereals, that are resistant to spectinomycin (~~Day and Goldschmidt Clermont 2011; Maliga and Bock 2011; Rosellini 2012; Bock 2015).~~

~~In fact, the selection phase is critical in plastid transformation: the transgenic plastome, initially present in one or a few copies in the transplastomic cell, must be amplified to homozygosity within the plastid, and at the same time the transgenic plastid must replicate and segregate in cell divisions to reach the homoplasmic state. The transition from the chimeric and heteroplasmic to the solid, homoplasmic state, is achieved thanks to a prolonged selection phase, that is, by carrying out two or three cycles of regeneration under selective pressure (Day and Goldschmidt Clermont 2011; Maliga and Bock 2011). The selection pressure is considered to be a key factor: too strong post-transformation selection can eliminate transformed cells, before resistance, that develops slowly, is reached; too weak selection can result in inability to select rare transformation events.~~

Gabaculine (3-amino-2,3-dihydrobenzoic acid) is a bacterial toxin that inhibits the glutamate 1-semialdehyde aminotransferase (GSA) (~~Grimm et al. 1991~~). GSA is an essential enzyme in all aerobic organisms, ~~because it catalyzes the conversion of glutamate 1-semialdehyde into aminolevulinic acid (ALA), a precursor of heme and tetrapyrrolic compounds, including~~

1 chlorophyll and phytochromes. In photosynthetic organisms, GSA is encoded in the nuclear
2 genome, but is active in the plastid.
3 Mutated GSA genes from *Synechococcus* or alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) have been used as SMGs
4 for nuclear transformation (Gough et al. 2001; Rosellini et al. 2007; Ferradini et al. 2011;
5 Giancaspro et al. 2012). ~~In the alfalfa gene, a point mutation (M286>I) in the cofactor binding~~
6 ~~domain was sufficient to confer gabaculine resistance to the enzyme (Ferradini et al. 2011).~~
7 In the attempt of developing a new, non antibiotic-based selection system for plastome
8 transformation, we introduced the *Synechococcus* mutant GSA gene (*hemL*) in the tobacco plastid
9 genome, together with the *aadA* gene for spectinomycin selection (Bellucci et al. 2015), ~~and we~~
10 ~~observed that gabaculine selection was not effective to directly regenerate transplastomic plants;~~
11 ~~however, once transgenic plants were selected using spectinomycin, they acquired gabaculine~~
12 ~~resistance during the 2nd and 3rd rounds of selection, and were brought to the homoplasmic~~
13 ~~condition. Based on this result,~~ ~~i~~In this work, we inserted ~~ed the a mutated~~ plant *MsGSAgr* gene
14 into the tobacco plastome to indirectly compare its performance with the bacterial *hemL* gene, thus
15 extending and confirming previous results.

17 **Materials and Methods**

19 *Gene constructs*

21 ~~A plastid transformation vector for *MsGSAgr* expression in tobacco plastids was virtually~~
22 ~~assembled using SnapGene Viewer version 4.2.~~ The 1416 bp coding sequence of the gabaculine
23 resistant mutant *MsGSAgr* gene from alfalfa, ~~taken from the pAPCK-*MsGSAgr* plasmid (Ferradini~~
24 ~~et al. 2011), was processed with the software ChloroP 1.1 (Emanuelsson et al. 1999,~~
25 ~~http://www.cbs.dtu.dk/services/ChloroP/).~~ A putative chloroplast transit peptide (tp) of 36 amino
26 acids was identified (Supplementary Fig. S1), but we removed 35 amino acids, doing a conservative
27 estimate of the transit peptide length; by adding ATG in 5', a 1314 bp coding sequence was
28 obtained.

29 Codon optimization for expression in the tobacco plastome was performed using the Optimum-
30 GeneTM algorithm at GenScript (Piscataway, NJ) and the resulting coding sequence was *in silico*
31 assembled with the tobacco 5' *psbA* (~~promoter and 5'UTR of the *psbA* gene~~). The 5'UTR-*MsGSAgr*
32 cassette was synthesized by GenScript (Piscataway, NJ 08854, USA) and digested with *EcoRV* and
33 *NoI* to be cloned into the *EcoRV/NoI* sites of the *pLD-CtV* tobacco chloroplast transformation
34 vector, downstream the *aadA* gene (Dhingra et al. 2004). The resulting *pLD-CtV-*MsGSAgr** vector,
35 where the *aadA* gene is under the control of the promoter of the tobacco 16S rRNA gene (Prn),
36 targets the insertion to the *trnI-trnA* intergenic region of the tobacco plastome (Supplementary Fig.
37 42).

39 *Transformation of the tobacco plastome and progeny tests*

41 Particle bombardment with the *pLD-CtV-*MsGSAgr** vector was carried out as described (Bellucci et
42 al. 2007) ~~on ten leaves obtained from *in vitro* grown, 6-week-old tobacco plants.~~ After being
43 cultured at 24°C for 2 days on RMOP medium, each leaf was split into two halves and each portion
44 was exposed to a different selection treatment: ~~Small sections derived from one portion were~~

1 ~~selected with~~ 500 mg L⁻¹ spectinomycin (~~Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany~~) ~~or, while those~~
2 ~~derived from the other portion were selected with~~ 50 µM gabaculine (~~DBA Italia, Segrate, Italy~~).
3 After 50–60 days of culture, with subcultures every 3 weeks, putative transplastomic shoots were
4 transferred under the same selection ~~in on~~ MS medium. No green plants were obtained with
5 gabaculine selection, thus, only plants regenerated in the presence of spectinomycin were used for a
6 2nd regeneration round. Leaf explants from these plants were split into two parts and selected on
7 spectinomycin or gabaculine, as described above. For the 3rd regeneration round, leaves obtained
8 from plants regenerated in RMOP containing spectinomycin were subcultured only in RMOP-
9 spectinomycin medium, and the plants regenerated on gabaculine were subcultured only with
10 gabaculine. T₀ plants regenerated both from the 2nd and the 3rd round of selection were then rooted
11 on MS selective medium at 16–8 h photoperiod under 60 µE m⁻² s⁻² light intensity at 24°C and
12 transferred to pots containing a sterile mixture of soil and peat (1:1) to self-pollinate and set seeds.
13 After surface sterilization, T₁ seeds were grown as described above on spectinomycin or gabaculine
14 MS media to assess homoplasmy. Two T₁ plants per event derived from the 3rd regeneration step
15 were allowed to self-fertilize and crossed as males and females to wild type plants to evaluate
16 maternal inheritance. T₂ seeds were germinated on selective media as described.

18 *PCR, Southern and northern blot analyses*

20 Total ~~plant~~ DNA was isolated from ~~50 mg of~~ young leaves using the GenElute™ Plant Genomic
21 DNA Miniprep kit (Merck KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany). PCR amplification was carried out using
22 the primer pairs P11/ H1MsGSA and 3P/3M (Supplementary Table 1).

23 For Southern blot analysis, total ~~plant~~ DNA was extracted from leaves and the hybridization was
24 carried out as described (Bellucci et al. 2000). Four micrograms of total DNA were digested with
25 *Bg*III. After electrophoretic fractionation in a 0.8 % agarose gel, DNA was then transferred to a
26 Hybond-XL nylon membrane (GE Healthcare, Chicago, Illinois, USA). A *trnI-trnA* intergenic
27 region of 650 bp was PCR-amplified from the tobacco genomic DNA with the primer pair
28 AlaB/16S-23S.1 (Supplementary Table 1) and was used as a probe. Total cellular RNA was
29 extracted from ~~plant~~ leaves with the NucleoSpin RNA Plant kit (Macherey-Nagel) ~~according to the~~
30 ~~manufacturer's instructions~~. The northern hybridization experiment was carried out as described in
31 Bellucci et al. (2000). ~~Briefly, 5 µg of RNA were separated by electrophoresis in a 1.4 %~~
32 ~~formaldehyde agarose gels and transferred to Hybond N nylon membranes (GE Healthcare,~~
33 ~~Chicago, Illinois, USA)~~. A probe was generated by digestion of the *pLD-CtV-MsGSAGr* vector with
34 *Nde*I and *Not*I, to obtain the *MsGSAGr* coding sequence. Hybridization was performed for both
35 DNA and RNA filters as indicated by the membrane supplier and the probes were labelled with
36 α[³²P]-dCTP by random priming using the Ready-To-Go™ kit (GE Healthcare, Chicago, Illinois,
37 USA).

39 **Results**

41 Spectinomycin selection resulted in the regeneration of 12 independent green shoots from
42 approximately 100 leaf pieces obtained cutting 10 half leaves. Six events (1.1, 3.1, 4.1, 5.1, 5.2, and
43 9.1) proved to be PCR positive and were advanced to the 2nd regeneration round. Five of these

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1 plants, apart from event 4.1, regenerated resistant shoots (Fig. 2), which were used to start a 3rd
2 round of regeneration.

3 Selection with gabaculine of the other 10 half leaves allowed the regeneration of many chlorotic
4 shoots, but no green, resistant shoots were obtained. ~~Nonetheless, about 15 vigorous shoots were
5 excised and transferred to gabaculine rooting media to better estimate the phenotype, but none of
6 them turned green. PCR analyses for the presence of the transgene construct gave negative results
7 (not shown). These results are like those previously obtained in tobacco with the bacterial mutant
8 GSA gene *hemL* (Bellucci et al. 2015).~~

9 Due to the impossibility of selecting gabaculine-resistant plant in the 1st regeneration round, some
10 leaves of the six plants selected with spectinomycin in the first regeneration round were also
11 subjected to gabaculine selection during the 2nd regeneration cycle. In sum, after the 2nd
12 regeneration round, five out of six PCR-positive events selected with spectinomycin confirmed to
13 be resistant (1.1, 3.1, 5.1, 5.2, and 9.1), whereas only three in six events (1.1, 5.2 and 9.1) were
14 resistant to gabaculine (Supplementary Fig. 23). Resistance appeared not to be complete, because
15 growth was reduced and shoot color was paler with respect to the spectinomycin selection
16 treatments, as described for the *hemL* gene (Bellucci et al. 2015). Moreover, a 3rd regeneration
17 round was carried out as described to grant that the homoplasmic state was reached. After the 2nd
18 and 3rd regeneration cycle, two plants per event were transferred to soil and ~~reared in pots to
19 flowering seeds were produced.~~

20 ~~Two events (5.2 and 9.1) were chosen to investigate in detail the transplastomic state by molecular
21 analyses.~~The 5.2 plants selected with gabaculine or spectinomycin starting from the 2nd
22 regeneration cycle were named 5.2g and 5.2s, respectively; the same applies to event 9.1 (9.1g and
23 9.1s).

24 The 5.2 and 9.1 T₀ events from the 2nd and 3rd regeneration rounds were PCR-positive, showing the
25 expected homologous integration, except for plant 9.1g, which appeared to have lost the transgenes
26 during the 3rd regeneration round (Fig. 31). ~~Indeed, the plastome of this plant did not have retained
27 the transgene constructs, as shown by the 3M/3P primer pair that amplified the sequence comprised
28 between the native 16S gene and the *aadA* gene in 9.1g during the 2nd regeneration, but later did not
29 amplify it any more. In addition, the amplicon of the P11/H1MsGSA primer pair, a DNA region
30 encompassing the two transgenes (Fig. 1), was absent as well.~~ Loss of the transformed plastomes
31 moving from the 2nd to the 3rd regeneration round in plant 9.1g was confirmed by restriction
32 fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis using a Southern hybridization experiment (Fig. 4
33 2 a-b). ~~As regards the 5.2 transformation event, a~~ After the 2nd regeneration, plant 5.2g was
34 heteroplasmic, as shown by the simultaneous presence of the two fragments of 5.2 and 2.1 kb plus
35 the additional 4.4 kb fragment typical of the wild-type chloroplast genome (Fig. 2). On the contrary,
36 plant 5.2s was homoplasmic because it showed only the 5.2 and 2.1 kb fragments. In the next
37 regeneration step, plant 5.2g became homoplasmic like ~~its sister line~~ 5.2s. Interestingly, the RFLP
38 analysis also revealed a genetic rearrangement occurred ~~to in~~ the 9.1 transformation event during
39 the first regeneration. In the 2nd regeneration round, 9.1g was heteroplasmic because the *trnI-trnA*
40 probe detected the expected 5.2 kb fragment and the 4.4 wild-type fragment, whereas 9.1s seemed
41 to be homoplasmic. Instead of the 2.1 fragment, after prolonged film exposure, a 3.5 kb fragment
42 became visible in these two plants (asterisk in Fig. 4b2b). Considering that they were PCR positive
43 for the P11/H1MsGSA primer pair (Fig. 31), this 3.5 kb fragment was indicative of a sequence
44 rearrangement close to the *MsGSAGr-trnA* region which involved only the *MsGSAGr* 3' sequence.

1 After the 3rd regeneration step, plant 9.1s was ~~still~~ homoplasmic. Instead, plant 9.1g showed only
2 the 4.4 kb wild-type fragment, confirming that the transformed plastomes were lost, ~~possibly~~
3 ~~because they were in a very few number compared to the wild type plastomes and/or 9.1g was~~
4 ~~chimeric and the tissues used for the 3rd regeneration were not transformed. Therefore, plants~~ Plants
5 9.1g and 9.1s ~~should~~ did not transcribe the *MsGSAgr* gene, ~~because the first plant was identical to a~~
6 ~~wild type plant and the second one did not have an intact *MsGSAgr* 3' gene copy,~~ as demonstrated
7 by northern hybridization analysis (Fig. ~~3e2c~~). An additional faint 4.5 kb fragment was visible in all
8 the homoplasmic plants, whereas in the heteroplasmic or wild-type plants ~~either it~~ was absent or
9 hidden by the more abundant 4.4 kb fragment (Fig. ~~4b2b~~). As already observed (Bellucci et al.
10 2015), this fragment could indicate a wild plastid DNA insertion in the nuclear genome or
11 recombination between the endogenous and the inserted Prn promoters (Rogalski et al. 2006; Li et
12 al. 2011; De Marchis et al. 2011).

13 ~~Overall, In summary,~~ only transplastomic event 5.2 originated homoplasmic plants with the two
14 selection systems, and both 5.2g and 5.2s transcribed the transgenes. The *MsGSAgr* probe detected
15 a main transcript of 1.7 kb corresponding to *MsGSAgr* mRNA, while two minor transcripts of 4.0
16 and 5.0 kb were ~~detected~~ evidenced, originated from read-through transcription upstream of the
17 *MsGSAgr* gene ~~and due to lack of efficient transcription termination~~ (Fig. ~~3e2c~~).

19 **Seed assays**

20
21 ~~To strengthen the results obtained by molecular analyses, seed assays with T₁ seeds collected on~~
22 ~~self fertilized T₀ plants after the 2nd and 3rd regeneration cycle were performed.~~ When germinated
23 on ~~MS medium containing both gabaculine and spectinomycin~~ selective media, T₁ seeds of plant
24 5.2g segregated resistant to susceptible seedlings after the 2nd regeneration round, revealing a
25 heteroplasmic nature of the transplastomic event, which became entirely resistant, i.e. homoplasmic,
26 after the 3rd round (Fig. ~~53~~). On the contrary, when germinated on the two toxins, 5.2s seeds showed
27 100% resistance already after the 2nd regeneration round. The T₁ progeny of plant 9.1s was resistant
28 to spectinomycin but not to gabaculine, after both the 2nd and 3rd rounds of selection on
29 spectinomycin. This means that plant 9.1s was already homoplasmic after the 2nd regeneration
30 round, and that the *MsGSAgr* gene was not functional, as suggested by both the results of northern
31 ~~and Southern~~ hybridizations, ~~which failed to show *MsGSAgr* mRNA, and by the 3.5 kb fragment in~~
32 ~~Fig. 4b.~~ The T₁ progeny of plant 9.1g was ~~always~~ susceptible to both spectinomycin and gabaculine.
33 Thus, we can hypothesize that this plant was chimeric and the reproductive organs originating the
34 T₁ seeds after the 2nd regeneration were non-transgenic. Leaf tissues of 9.1g cultured for the 3rd
35 regeneration round were non-transformed or, alternatively, were heteroplasmic (as shown in Fig.
36 ~~42~~), but the transgenes were not selected during cell divisions and plant regeneration. To verify that
37 plants 1.1g and 1.1s did not escape from toxin selection (as was the case for 9.1g), their T₁
38 progenies, obtained from plants regenerated after the 3rd cycle were germinated on selective media
39 as described, and were 100 % resistant (data not shown).

40 To demonstrate maternal inheritance of the transgenes, T₂ seedlings obtained by selfing and
41 crossing T₁ plants derived from the 3rd regeneration round of the transplastomic plant 5.2g were
42 grown in selective conditions (Supplementary Fig. 64). Non-transgenic seedlings were 100 %
43 susceptible to both toxins, whereas seedlings originated from the 5.2g x NT cross were completely
44 resistant to spectinomycin and gabaculine, both alone or combined. ~~Conversely~~ As expected, lack of

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1 resistance was shown in the reciprocal cross, excluding the possibility of expression from nuclear
2 integration.-

4 **Discussion and conclusion**

6 In a previous report, we tested the bacterial *hemL* gene, encoding a gabaculine resistant GSA, for its
7 potential to provide an *in vitro* selection system for plastome transformation of tobacco (Bellucci et
8 al. 2015). Here, after codon optimization for tobacco plastome expression, we used the plant
9 ortholog isolated from alfalfa, *MsGSAgr*, in the attempt to improve the results obtained with the
10 bacterial gene. In conclusion, We have found shown that In fact, with the *hemL* gene, gabaculine
11 selection permitted to obtain 3 homoplasmic events (60 %) in 5 events initially selected with
12 spectinomycin (Bellucci et al. 2015). With the *MsGSAgr* gene, in this work, we had similar results:
13 out of five events regenerated with spectinomycin selection, three were advanced through
14 gabaculine selection, even if only two (40 %) resistant homoplasmic events (1.1g and 5.2g) were
15 finally obtained.

16 Like the bacterial *hemL* encoded enzyme, the mutant plant GSA enzyme is either incompletely
17 resistant to gabaculine or expressed at an insufficient level in the plastid for selection during the
18 post bombardment phase of the plastid transformation process in tobacco.

19 In one event (plant 9.1g), loss of the transformed plastomes was observed during selection cycles on
20 gabaculine. On the contrary, the corresponding line selected in spectinomycin (9.1s) was
21 homoplasmic after the 2nd regeneration step, even if the *MsGSAgr* gene was not functional due to
22 partial gene rearrangement or loss, as already reported for transplastomic plants obtained with the
23 *pLD-CtV* transformation vector (Bellucci et al. 2007; 2015). In addition, comparison of the
24 evolution of plasmid state between 5.2s and 5.2g (as shown by Southern hybridization results and
25 progeny test) indicates that the progress towards homoplasmy is slower with gabaculine than with
26 spectinomycin: two regeneration rounds were sufficient when selecting with the antibiotic, whereas
27 three cycles were necessary with gabaculine selection (considering that the first regeneration was
28 obtained using spectinomycin and only the next two with gabaculine). Therefore, it seems that
29 phytotoxicity of gabaculine was too mild to consistently grant effective transplastome amplification.
30 However, it became effective once its copy number is amplified thanks to antibiotic resistance
31 conferred by the *aadA* SMG. In fact, *MsGSAgr* was capable to confer gabaculine resistance and
32 attain the homoplasmic state in events 1.1 and 5.2.

33 In conclusion, we have shown that *MsGSAgr*, like *hemL*, behaves as a 'secondary' SMGs, as
34 several other ~~genes~~ SMGs described in the literature (Daniell et al. 1998; Ye et al. 2001; Iamtham
35 and Day 2000; Lutz et al. 2001; Falk et al. 2005; Dufourmantel et al. 2007; Fernandez-San Millan et
36 al. 2011; Gisby et al. 2012). Optimization efforts on the plant *MsGSAgr* gene can be worthwhile,
37 turning to plant species that are more sensitive to gabaculine with respect to tobacco, and still
38 recalcitrant to plastid transformation.

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8

1 **Figure Captions**

2
3
4 **Fig. 1** PCR analyses. The genomic DNA of T₀ events 5.2 and 9.1 from the 2nd and 3rd rounds of
5 regeneration on gabaculine (g) or spectinomycin (s) was amplified with the 3M/3P or
6 P11/H1MsGSA primer pairs producing the expected 1.65 or 0.64 kb amplicons, respectively. Event
7 9.1 seems to have lost the transgenes between the 2nd and 3rd rounds when selected on gabaculine.
8 m: molecular weight marker, PI: plasmid *pLD-CiV-MsGSAgr*, c: no DNA, NT: non-transgenic plant
9

10
11 **Fig. 2** Southern and northern blot analyses of two T₀ transformation events after two (2nd) or three
12 (3rd) regeneration rounds on selective media (s: spectinomycin, g: gabaculine), using the *trnI-trnA*
13 region or the *MsGSAgr* coding sequence as probes, respectively. a: The 5.2 and 2.1 fragments are
14 indicative of the presence of the transgenic constructs, whereas the 4.4 kb band is the non-
15 transgenic RFLP. A faint 4.5 kb fragment was present in the transplastomic homoplasmic plants,
16 likely deriving from recombination between duplicated sequences or plastid-wild DNA insertion in
17 the nucleus. After the 2nd regeneration, only plants 5.2s and 9.1s were homoplasmic, while plant
18 5.2g became homoplasmic in the next regeneration step. Conversely, plant 9.1g moved from a
19 heteroplasmic state to a non-transgenic state. b: the same blot was exposed for a longer time. *: a
20 3.5 kb fragment that likely represents a genetic rearrangement of the *MsGSAgr-trnA* region. c)
21 northern hybridization analysis with total RNA extracted from the same plants of (a). Several
22 transcripts of different length were obtained due to chloroplast readthrough transcription. rRNA
23 stained by ethidium bromide is shown as a loading control and the 25S and 18S ribosomal RNA are
24 indicated. NT: non-transgenic plant
25

26 **Fig. 3** Spectinomycin and gabaculine resistance of T₁ seedlings obtained by selfing T₀ plants of
27 events 5.2 and 9.1 from the 2nd and 3rd rounds of regeneration. When selected on both selection
28 systems, plant 5.2g segregated resistant (green seedlings) and susceptible plants (yellow seedlings
29 in gabaculine and white seedlings in spectinomycin) after the 2nd round, while produced 100%
30 resistant progeny after the 3rd round. When event 5.2 was selected on spectinomycin, 5.2s produced
31 a 100% resistant progeny after both the 2nd and 3rd rounds. Event 9.1 was susceptible to both
32 chemicals when selected on gabaculine, whereas it was spectinomycin-resistant and gabaculine-
33 susceptible when selected on spectinomycin. Letters g (for gabaculine) or s (for spectinomycin)
34 following event numbers on the left indicate the selective agent used during the 2nd and 3rd
35 regeneration rounds. NT: non-transgenic plant
36

1 **Key message**

2 Resistance to the phytotoxin gabaculine was obtained in tobacco by introducing a mutant plant gene
3 in the plastid genome; it may be implemented as a tool in plastid genetic transformation.

4

